

Supplementary material of the article:

“Multi-country and intersectoral assessment of cluster congruence between pipelines for genomics surveillance of foodborne pathogens”

Study design:

- **Supplementary Data 1.** Details on the study design.

L. monocytogenes:

- **Supplementary Data 2.** Details on pipeline performance and inter-pipeline cluster congruence analysis at all threshold levels for *L. monocytogenes*, including the heatmaps for each pairwise comparison.
- **Supplementary Data 3.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of an *L. monocytogenes* ST into a single cluster.
- **Supplementary Data 4.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of an *L. monocytogenes* CC into a single cluster.
- **Supplementary Data 5.** Inter-pipeline corresponding points for each pairwise comparison performed for *L. monocytogenes*.
- **Supplementary Data 6.** Details on the r^2 and slope of the linear tendency line that fits the inter-pipeline corresponding points presented in Supplementary Data 5.
- **Supplementary Data 7.** Number of clusters detected by each allele-based pipeline at high resolution level in *L. monocytogenes* dataset, with indication of the number of clusters detected with the exact same composition in all pipelines (exact_composition_all) or in at least another pipeline (shared_with_another), or not detected by another pipeline (exclusive).
- **Supplementary Data 8.** Clusters detected by at least one allele-based pipeline at 7 ADs in the *L. monocytogenes* dataset, with indication of the cluster length and the minimum AD threshold at which this cluster was detected by each pipeline.
- **Supplementary Data 9.** Percentage of *L. monocytogenes* genetic clusters that once detected by a given pipeline at a certain threshold (left) are also detected, with the exact same composition, by another pipeline (top) at another (or up to another) threshold.

S. enterica:

- **Supplementary Data 10.** Details on pipeline performance and inter-pipeline cluster congruence analysis at all threshold levels for *S. enterica*, including the heatmaps for each pairwise comparison.
- **Supplementary Data 11.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of an *S. enterica* serotype into a single cluster.
- **Supplementary Data 12.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of an *S. enterica* ST into a single cluster.

- **Supplementary Data 13.** Inter-pipeline corresponding points for each pairwise comparison performed for *S. enterica*.
- **Supplementary Data 14.** Details on the r^2 and slope of the linear tendency line that fits the inter-pipeline corresponding points presented in Supplementary Data 13.
- **Supplementary Data 15.** Number of clusters detected by each allele-based pipeline at high resolution level in *S. enterica* dataset, with indication of the number of clusters detected with the exact same composition in all pipelines (exact_composition_all) or in at least another pipeline (shared_with_another), or not detected by another pipeline (exclusive).
- **Supplementary Data 16.** Clusters detected by at least one allele-based pipeline at 14 ADs in the *S. enterica* dataset, with indication of the cluster length and the minimum AD threshold at which this cluster was detected by each pipeline.
- **Supplementary Data 17.** Percentage of *S. enterica* genetic clusters that once detected by a given pipeline at a certain threshold (left) are also detected, with the exact same composition, by another pipeline (top) at another (or up to another) threshold.
- **Supplementary Data 18.** Genetic distance within the *S. enterica* genetic clusters detected at 14 ADs by the INNUENDO-like-INNUENDO99 pipeline before and after a dynamic cluster zoom-in.

***E. coli*:**

- **Supplementary Data 19.** Details on pipeline performance and inter-pipeline cluster congruence analysis at all threshold levels for *E. coli*, including the heatmaps for each pairwise comparison.
- **Supplementary Data 20.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of an *E. coli* serotype into a single cluster.
- **Supplementary Data 21.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of an *E. coli* ST into a single cluster.
- **Supplementary Data 22.** Inter-pipeline corresponding points for each pairwise comparison performed for *E. coli*.
- **Supplementary Data 23.** Details on the r^2 and slope of the linear tendency line that fits the inter-pipeline corresponding points presented in Supplementary Data 22.
- **Supplementary Data 24.** Number of clusters detected by each allele-based pipeline at high resolution level in *E. coli* dataset, with indication of the number of clusters detected with the exact same composition in all pipelines (exact_composition_all) or in at least another pipeline (shared_with_another), or not detected by another pipeline (exclusive).
- **Supplementary Data 25.** Clusters detected by at least one allele-based pipeline at 9 ADs in the *E. coli* dataset, with indication of the cluster length and the minimum AD threshold at which this cluster was detected by each pipeline.
- **Supplementary Data 26.** Percentage of *E. coli* genetic clusters that once detected by a given pipeline at a certain threshold (left) are also detected, with the exact same composition, by another pipeline (top) at another (or up to another) threshold.

- **Supplementary Data 27.** Genetic distance within the *E. coli* genetic clusters detected at 9 ADs by the INNUENDO-like-INNUENDO99 pipeline before and after a dynamic cluster zoom-in.

***C. jejuni*:**

- **Supplementary Data 28.** Details on pipeline performance and inter-pipeline cluster congruence analysis at all threshold levels for *C. jejuni*, including the heatmaps for each pairwise comparison.
- **Supplementary Data 29.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of a *C. jejuni* CC into a single cluster.
- **Supplementary Data 30.** Minimum threshold (AD) at which each allele-based pipeline groups all samples of a *C. jejuni* ST into a single cluster.
- **Supplementary Data 31.** Inter-pipeline corresponding points for each pairwise comparison performed for *C. jejuni*.
- **Supplementary Data 32.** Details on the r^2 and slope of the linear tendency line that fits the inter-pipeline corresponding points presented in Supplementary Data 31.
- **Supplementary Data 33.** Number of clusters detected by each allele-based pipeline at high resolution level in *C. jejuni* dataset, with indication of the number of clusters detected with the exact same composition in all pipelines (exact_composition_all) or in at least another pipeline (shared_with_another), or not detected by another pipeline (exclusive).
- **Supplementary Data 34.** Clusters detected by at least one allele-based pipeline at 4 ADs in the *C. jejuni* dataset, with indication of the cluster length and the minimum AD threshold at which this cluster was detected by each pipeline.
- **Supplementary Data 35.** Percentage of *C. jejuni* genetic clusters that once detected by a given pipeline at a certain threshold (left) are also detected, with the exact same composition, by another pipeline (top) at another (or up to another) threshold.
- **Supplementary Data 36.** Genetic distance within the *C. jejuni* genetic clusters detected at 4 ADs by the INNUENDO-like-INNUENDO99 and the SeqSphere-wgMLST pipelines before and after a dynamic cluster zoom-in.

Impact of changing pipeline components:

- **Supplementary Data 37.** Details on the assessment of the impact of applying a different assembly pipeline and updating the allele caller.

Schemas:

- **Supplementary Data 38.** Details on the schemas used by each pipeline.